

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Emission Reductions in Fuel Production Using CCS

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Image courtesy: [CEENERGYNEWS](#)

About this document:

This document outlines a possible approach to reducing fossil emissions associated with the production and use of transportation fuels beyond switching from fossil fuels to fuels produced from biomass. The description is encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP), where the 'Neutral' descriptor indicate that these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to decarbonisation challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions. The intended audience for this document includes policymakers, stakeholders in the energy sector, and city administrators.

Description:

Transportation plays an important role in our global economy and is essentially provided through “vehicles” using fossil hydrocarbons. To reduce the fossil emissions related with the production and use of such fuels, biomass can be used as a feedstock to partially or fully replace the fossil feedstock in the refinery. The biogenic feedstock can come from various biomass resources, such as agricultural waste, forestry residues, algae, and energy crops, and it is important that it is sustainably sourced. The biomass can then be used to produce a wide range of valuable products, including fuels for aviation and heavy trucks. Some of the biomass is consumed by the refinery, to provide energy to the production process, which leads to emissions of CO₂. When applying CCS to biogenic emissions it could have the effect of net removal of CO₂ from the biosphere. This is known as ‘negative emissions’ or ‘Carbon Dioxide Removal’ (CDR). However, it is important to know that only a fraction (4-8%) of the total emissions related to fuel, from resource extraction to use in a vehicle, is related to the production of the fuel. The majority of the life-cycle emissions occur with the use of the fuel.

Billions of tons of cargo are transported around the world each year by trucks, planes, ships, and trains, accounting for up to 8% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) and up to 11% if warehouses and ports are included. Growing economies in Asia, Africa, and Latin America are expected to triple global demand for freight by 2050, which will double GHG emissions. Unfortunately, even today nearly all freight transportation runs on oil and gas, and with e-Commerce and home delivery growing further, freight will become the highest emitting sector

by 2050 unless strong measures are taken. A product value chain analysis can show both emission reductions and cost increases associated with a potential implementation of CCS: from the resource extraction and production to the use of the fuel. As in this case, emission reductions associated with production and consumption of fuels for airfreight and heavy trucks are explored; the aim is to analyse the impact that a reduction in fossil emissions from the oil refinery would have on the total fuel value chain.

Goal:

Efficient integration of CO₂ capture in refineries to explore how that affects emission reductions and costs along the whole fuel value chain (from resource extraction to fuel use). The goal is to reduce fossil emissions from fuel production. When part or all of the fossil feedstock is replaced biomass, the fossil emissions from the use of the fuel can also be reduced.

Solution:

Fossil emissions related to fuel production and fuel use can be reduced by applying CCS to the refinery and by replacing part or all of the fossil feedstock with biomass. Since the refinery only accounts for 4-8% of emissions through the whole fuel value chain, CCS has a limited impact on life-cycle emissions on its own. Replacing the fossil feedstock with biomass has a larger impact on reducing fossil emissions. These two solutions can reduce total life-cycle emissions of the fuel, from resource extraction to fuel use, by 3-23% when assuming that 20% of the fossil feedstock is replaced with biomass (Hörbe Emanuelsson & Johnsson, 2023).

Barriers to development:

Competitiveness of market prices: more costly compared to fuels produced without CCS and with fossil feedstock. Transparency along the value chain: biomass must be sustainably sourced to ensure emission reductions.

Cooperation and participation among all actors along the value chain are crucial to ensure the balance and prevent the production of lower fossil emission materials without market demand.

Furthermore, the majority of CCS projects today are economically challenged, with high costs of capture for dilute point sources and a limited number of revenue streams available.

Enablers to development:

Enablers for development, on the other hand, include the green labelling of fuels if they are produced completely from biomass, potential structural changes, and government support in the aviation industry, rising CO₂ prices, phasing out free allocation of emission allowances within the EU-ETS (for fossil fuels). The demand for negative emissions in the voluntary carbon market also serves as a driving force for beneficial change, in the case where part or all of the feedstock is biomass. If negative emissions are achieved, they could be sold on the voluntary carbon market, thus balancing the increased cost with implementing CCS at the refinery.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Technology: The increasing availability of CCS technologies provides the potential to	Economic Benefits: Marginal potential for creating new markets and job opportunities in the green technology sector.

achieve CO ₂ emissions reductions from fuel production reductions.	
Market demand for sustainability: Growing consumer and business preference for environmentally responsible transport services.	High initial costs: Significant investment required for the development, infrastructure, and integration of CCS technology into existing systems.
Environmental benefits: A small potential for reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, along the fuel value chain.	Supply: Limited availability of biomass for fuel production, to replace fossil feedstock.
Opportunities	Threats
Policy Support: Potential for increased government support and favourable policies, including subsidies and tax incentives for the adoption of CCS.	Market competition: Competition in the transport industry, which may prioritise cost over sustainability in the short term.
Technological innovation: Opportunities for breakthroughs in CCS implementation.	Economic fluctuations: Sensitivity to economic downturns that can reduce investment in sustainability initiatives.
Expansion of carbon markets: Growth in voluntary and compliance carbon markets, creating demand for carbon credits generated through CCS, and, in the case of use of biomass, CDR.	Public perception risks: Potential for public scepticism or opposition to CCS projects due to perceived environmental risks or ineffectiveness.
	Regulatory changes: Risk of regulatory changes or lack of international consensus on CCS standards and carbon accounting, affecting project viability.
	Oil and gas producers: Countries which extract oil and gas conduct their activities at a rate which is not aligned with the Paris Agreement.

End of 2023, the 28th United Nations Climate Change Conference, the COP28, was held, where serious concerns about the global climate trajectory were expressed in consideration of the hottest year 2023, yet to be recorded. The final agreement in which parties settled on focused on a just transition away from fossil fuels and toward a green and fair economy, which should be further achieved ‘in a just, orderly and equitable manner’. Simultaneously, a call for tripling the global renewable energy capacity and doubling the current energy efficiency by 2030 was expressed, which includes the development and implementation of numerous zero- and low-emission technologies.

According to the Global CCS Institute, the COP28 served as an opportunity to reaffirm the importance of scaling carbon management technologies, such as CCUS, in a variety of industries, paving a way forward for innovative new projects in this area.

Lessons learned/ Impact:

Direct and indirect benefits that are identified:

- Only using CCS at refineries have a limited impact on fossil emission reductions through the fuel value chain since the refineries only accounts for 4-8% of total life-cycle emissions from resource extraction to use.

- The cost increase on the fuel when implementing CCS in refineries can be as low as 6%. However, replacing 20% of the fossil feedstock with biomass can increase the cost of the fuel with 30-40% depending on the price of biogenic feedstock (Hörbe Emanuelsson & Johnsson, 2023).

The key success factor is the importance of establishing cooperation and partnerships along the value chain. This facilitates risk sharing and aligns the pace of adoption for successful implementation, for example, by establishing so-called CCS hubs, which are clusters of emission facilities that share the same CO₂ transportation and storage or use infrastructure.

There have been several recent government funding calls for hub developments in Canada, Europe, and the United States to address industrial emissions and accelerate the development of both carbon removal technology, in the case of using only biogenic feedstock, and infrastructure. There are approximately 15 CCS hubs worldwide in various stages of development and many more are being planned.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Perspectives on the Value of BECCS: The Cost of Bio-Energy Carbon Capture and Storage in the pulp and paper supply chain	Jonathan Klement	2019	<u>Chalmers University of Technology</u>
Supply Chain Driven Commercialisation of Bio Energy Carbon Capture and Storage	Jonathan Klement Johan Rootzén Fredrik Normann Filip Johnsson	2021	<u>Frontiers</u>
The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage – A product value chain analysis	Anna Hörbe Emanuelsson, Filip Johnsson	2023	<u>MDPI</u>
Freight Transportation	Climate Portal	2023	<u>MIT Climate Portal</u>
The world needs to capture, use, and store gigatons of CO ₂ : Where and how?	Phil de Luna et al.	2023	<u>McKinsey</u>

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Hörbe Emanuelsson A, Johnsson F.. (2023). The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage—
A Product Value Chain Analysis. *Energies*. 16(20):7113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16207113>